

LITERARY INTERPRETATION OF MOTHER-CHILD RELATIONSHIP IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article gives informations about the interpretation of one of the human relationships, the relationship between mothers and children, in Uzbek literature. The importance of mothers in upbringing children, morality and finding; their place in life is revealed by the example of the heroes of the artistic work. The character of the children who lost their mother's life due to their wrongdoing is "Ufq" ("Horizon"), "Oftoboyim" by Said Ahmad, "Qorako'z Majnun", in the works of O'tkir Hashimov's "Urushning so'nggi qurboni" ("The Last Victim of the War"); the images of mothers who did not give appropriate upbringing to their children were given in such works, Sh. Botayev's "Sho'rodan qolgan odamlar" ("People left from Shura"), Behbudi's "Padarkush"; the image of a well-educated child is highlighted in U. Hashimov's work "World Affairs

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If the main subject of fiction is a person, the event that concretizes this subject is the interpretation of relationships between people. A person cannot live without relationships, just as he cannot live apart from society. And fiction is a reflection of life. In this analysis, we turn to the artistic interpretation of the relationship between mothers and children, which is part of family relationships.

In Uzbek literature, we can find the relationship between mothers and children in a number of works. In the following works, the child somehow causes the death of his mother. In particular, in the story "The Last Victim of War" by Utkir Hashimov, Shoikrom leaves the other end of the electric wire between the strawberry furrows to protect his strawberries from thieves. Look at the sight, this wire is attached to the leg of his own mother Umri. From one point of view, it seems that Shoikrom has no sin, he would not have done this in both worlds when he knew that his mother would enter the strawberry field. He wanted to buy food for the children with the money he bought the strawberries. Society wanted to protect the last strawberries in his house from the thieves who took away his cow. Looking at the other side of the coin, why did Aunt Umri steal the

strawberry? For himself? No, he did this to buy milk for his dying son Shonemat . The mother wanted to exchange a handful of strawberries for milk and put a cup of hot milk in her son's mouth. He could have asked his son Shaikrom for this strawberry, but when he went to his son's place at night, he did not want to see his daughter-in-law because there was no food left. Even though his son knows that his wife is lying, he comforts himself by saying this to warm the children in the morning. The child is begging his mother for the leftover food, and the mother is stealing her son's money for her sick child.

In the "Horizon" trilogy of the writer Said Ahmad, what killed aunt Jannat was grief over the dishonor and unfortunate fate of her son. She carries food to the grove secretly with a kettle filled with boiling water around her waist so that my child can drink a cup of tea . Tursunboy waits not for his mother but for the food she brings. Even when he sees his mother being carried away, he regrets that there is no one to bring him food, not because he was separated from his mother, let alone to follow her to her final destination. In the story "Qorako'z Majnun" mother Saodat abandons her son Borikhan. So, can the Uzbek mother, created by Said Ahmed, give up her offspring? Aunt Jannat did not give up her cowardly son who ran away from the war, and mother Saodat .. Because Tursunboy's sin is less than Borikhan . Tursunboy was only a coward, his will was weak, and Borikhon left the religion and accepted the religion of the infidels, forgetting his language and identity. There is such an episode in the play. The story of Mother Saodat Borikhon's childhood clothes being taken out to the yard and burned. In fact, she tries to burn the memories of her son by adding them to her clothes. Mother Saodat's death is also caused by her son's actions. In this case, the son's attitude towards his mother is different from the above works. In the play, the father is a puppet of the Soviets, and the boy has committed a bitter crime against him. The mother cooks dough and gives it to her son in prison, and the boy keeps half of the bread and sugar given to him in prison for his mother. When he was brought to his mother, his mother was dead.

"He wouldn't notice even if a piece of coal was poured into his palms, no matter what. His tears dried up and his mind wandered away. His son was sitting in the corner. His son often sat quietly reading various books. Crying, he began to turn the pages of the book as his son used to read. Then he began to smell every page. He groped with his fingers. It was as if he was looking for the light of his son's eyes. It was as if he was trying to find his son's fingerprints and smear them on his eyes." This mother in the work is illiterate, has no independent opinion, is almost ignorant of the outside world, but like all

mothers, she has a feeling of love for her child. The character of this mother in the play is able to love her child, but she is not able to raise him as a perfect child. Why did Tashmurad steal? Because there is no one to guide him. He was confused about what to do after finishing school. He goes to his uncle when he doesn't get advice from his parents. His uncle also steals because he doesn't care about his fate. This situation reminds me of Behbudi's drama "Padarkush". Even then, the father is indifferent. His mother joined him. When the child caused the father's death, the mother cursed him: "Damn, Tashmurad, I wish you would go away with smallpox." But it was too late. Mother lost her child along with her husband. Her child was a victim of ignorance. In contrast to the work "People left from Shura", books give a child the upbringing that parents could not give. Because of this, he was able to set his father on the right path in the end.

I think that the most important thing in the relationship between mothers and children is the issue of education. Education of a mother to her child. In the above two works, mothers are weak in this matter. That's why Abdurauf Fitrat said in his work "Family": "The main tragedy of us Turkestans is that we do not educate our women and look down on them." That is why the Jadids first of all put forward the idea of enlightening mothers and women. A child receives education first of all from his mother. We can see the most beautiful upbringing of an Uzbek mother in Utkir Hashimov's "World Affairs".

In the play, Poshshakhan tells her children the story of how the eyes of the incompetent brothers turned into blind birds, and only then did the brothers realize that they need each other and cannot call each other at night. will give.

"Poor mother, when you were telling that sad tale, did you want the five children who were lying with their heads out of the blanket to be friendly with each other, like the swallow that croaked from its nest? Mothers want their children to always be together. And fate will blow you away. "Life is not kind to mothers even in this matter," it is said.

In the work, the author remembers the two myths that his mother told him in his childhood: about the sun and the sky: "When I think about it, these two myths that my mother told me when I was a child are as simple as life, as deep as life." Mother's upbringing is extremely important in human life in the fate of Khoja in this work. Thinker says to his friend Khoja: "He is a very quiet boy, his eyes are always sparkling." After hearing from the author 's father : "Egamberdi is burnt to death, I am coming from Chirchik. His son was caught while picking pockets," he said: "This is a lie, there is no better boy in the world than Khoja.

The boss can't be bad. Who knows ? "The laws of life do not always obey our wishes," he regrets.

So, what was the reason for such a meek and innocent Khoja to become a thief? Undoubtedly, his mother's upbringing. Khoja's mother fled to Chirchik with a man when her husband went to war. Later, she also took her child with her. Years later, this unpleasant news reached the villagers. So, his upbringing was not good during the past years.

The character of the Khoja's mother, Rano, that is, a treacherous woman in the work, is continued in a larger scale in the writer's novel "Between Two Doors". She is the mother of the main character Muzaffar, the wife of brother Shamurod, who returned from the war wounded. She leaves her three-month-old baby in the field and goes with Umar lawyer. Rano also realizes that her real happiness is her child. But it will be too late.

Writer wants to show that mother's heart bleeds in this situation. Because this is the field where the mother forced her daughter-in-law to set herself on fire, orphaned her grandchildren, and enslaved her son for life. Rather, he understood that it was the invaders who owned his field. In fact, the mother does not curse the child, but curses the captivity, curses the invasion., different aspects of the relationship between mothers and children from the point of view of literary studies is of particular importance in the formation of the worldview of the young generation.

In conclusion, Studying the relationship between mothers and children in literature is important in raising the feelings of kindness, which are rare today, and in the matter of morality and education.

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